

OXIDATION BEHAVIOUR AND MECHANISMS OF CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The oxidation behaviour of carbon/carbon composites was investigated. The oxidation reaction shows two mechanisms: surface reaction controlling mechanism and gaseous diffusion controlling mechanism. The coefficients of fitting equations during surface reaction controlling stage could be divided into three parts: rate constant, activation energy, and temperature terms. Results showed that the rate constant and activation energy terms could be correlated to the intrinsic properties of specimens.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced carbon matrix material (carbon/carbon composites, C/C) has been a leading candidate of material for high performance applications due to its outstanding characteristics including the high strength at elevated temperature, low density, high vaporization temperature, multiformity and the resistance to thermal shock¹⁻⁴.

Although C/C composite possesses excellent properties, the most serious weakness is the poor oxidation resistance. Thus, the unprotected C/C composites will be gasified rapidly in air at temperature as low as 500°C⁵. Suitable antioxidation protection is necessary for C/C composites to avoid oxidation reactions.

The oxidation reactions of C/C materials could be divided into two steps⁶⁻⁹:

1. gas phase diffusion across the boundary layer, and
2. reaction at the surface.

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The diffusivity of inward oxygen diffusion and outward CO, CO₂ diffusion is a function of temperature; therefore, the temperature is the predominant factor that affects the oxidation reaction rate in a specific test environment. At low to moderate temperature, the reactions at the surface were the rate controlling step for oxidation. The oxidation rates increase exponentially with temperature¹⁰. The activation energy of carbon-oxygen reactions could be acquired from Arrhenius equation by plotting logarithm of oxidation rates versus 1/T during the reaction controlling step^{6,8-10}.

The analysis of oxidation reaction rates in this study includes the activation energy term and the other terms. All of the terms could be substituted by the function of temperature, the rates could be fitted by the following two equations :

$$\ln r = A_0 + \frac{A_1}{T} \quad (1)$$

$$\ln r = B_0 + \frac{B_1}{T} + B_2 \ln T \quad (2)$$

where r is reaction rate; T is temperature; A_0, A_1, B_0, B_1, B_2 are fitting coefficients. Various composites with different structures were compared in this study.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Three types of C/C composites were adopted in this study as following :

CC1000 : the C/C composites were carbonized at 1000°C.

CVI1000 : the C/C composites were carbonized at 1000°C and densified via chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) method at 1000°C.

CC2600 : the C/C composites were carbonized at 1000°C and then graphitized at 2600°C .

Oxidation kinetic analysis:

The diagram of the thermogravimetric measurement is shown in Figure 1. The isothermal oxidation tests were taken at 600, 700, 800, 900 and 1000°C in air. The relationships between weight loss and oxidation time were recorded and the oxidation rate and oxidation temperature are correlated. The Arrhenius equation was used to obtain the activation energy. The dynamic oxidation tests were carried out with a heating rate of 5, 7.5, and 10°C/min from room temperature to 1100°C. The weight-time data collected from computer were converted to the oxidation rate-oxidation temperature relationship by suitable processes. The relationships between

reaction rates and oxidation temperature will be fitted to the equations (1) and (2) by a linear regression method to acquire the specific coefficients for various types of C/C composites.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Isothermal and non-isothermal oxidation tests for CC1000

The relationships between weight loss and oxidation time at various temperatures during isothermal oxidation tests for CC1000 are shown in Figure 2. The weight loss profile is nearly proportional to the square of time. The oxidation rates for various times are plotted as solid circle in Figure 3. The profiles of oxidation rates could be fitted by two linear equations. The oxidation rates at higher temperature (about 700-1000°C) could be fitted by a horizontal straight line and could be considered as a constant for any temperature; on the other hand, the rates at lower temperature (about 500-700°C) could be fitted by a straight line. These results imply that oxidation reactions are controlled by two mechanisms: diffusion rates and surface reactions during higher and lower temperature ranges, respectively. The slope of the linear fitting equation during surface carbon-oxygen reaction controlled oxidation stage was $-\Delta E/R$; where ΔE is the activation energy and R is the gas constant (1.987 kcal/mole K). Therefore, the activation energy of oxidation reaction of C/C composites was calculated as 44.3 kcal/mole by the isothermal oxidation methods.

The non-isothermal oxidation for CC1000 were conducted from room temperature to 1100°C with heating rates of 5, 7.5, and 10°C/min. The oxidation rate-temperature data were converted from the weight-time data and plotted in Figure 3. At the beginning (lower temperature) of the non-isothermal oxidation tests, there was slight weight loss for carbonized C/C composites (CC1000), and the rates were lower than 10^{-6} g/g sec. The oxidation rates increased very rapidly during 570-700, 545-725, 505-730°C for the heating rates at 5, 7.5, 10°C/min, respectively.

It is obvious to divide the oxidation rate profiles into three parts: slight oxidation stage, vigorous oxidation stage, and diffusion behavior stage. The slight and steady weight loss during lower temperature (below 500°C) was due to the oxidation reaction that might take place over the surface of the non-crystalline carbon structure. The outer carbon atoms associated with higher free energy were easily reacted with oxygen, but the temperature in this stage was not high enough to cause the extensive oxidation and rapid by weight loss.

When the temperature is higher than 500°C, the oxidation rates start to increase. The rates increase with temperature and the logarithm of oxidation rates was likely to increase exponentially with the reciprocal of the temperature.

When the diffusion rates of the gaseous reactants and products were slower than the surface carbon-oxygen reactions, the diffusion rates became the rate-limiting steps for the oxidation of

CC1000 above 700°C. Although the diffusivity was still a function of temperature and could be expressed as an Arrhenius equation, the temperature factor showed little effect on the diffusion rates. The rates kept almost constant as about 10^{-4} g/g sec, there were some tendencies to decrease.

The activation energy of the oxidation reaction could be acquired by fitting with the equations (1) and (2) (the former is an Arrhenius equation) and the values were 48.53 and 45.47 kcal/mole, respectively. The coefficient, B_2 , of the fitting equation (2) was 2.61, and that could imply that the surface area, gas concentration and the oxidation time were proportional to $T^{2.61}$.

Non-isothermal Oxidation tests for CC1000, CVI1000, CC2600

The non-isothermal oxidation tests with a heating rate of 10°C/min were conducted by observing the oxidation behaviors of CC1000, CVI1000, and CC2600. The oxidation data profiles of these specimens are shown in Figure 4. The different oxidation mechanisms, surface reaction controlled step and gaseous diffusion rate controlled step, can be distinguished from the profiles of oxidation rates in non-isothermal oxidation tests. The vigorous surface carbon-oxygen reactions began at 570, 720 and 700°C for CC1000, CVI1000, and CC2600, respectively. On the other hand, the oxidation reaction controlled by gaseous diffusion rate began at 700, 850, 920°C, respectively.

The coefficients of the two fitting equations (1 and 2) for the oxidation profiles of the surface oxygen-carbon reactions controlled stages are listed in Table 1. The coefficients of A_1 and B_1 included the activation energy terms, hence various activation energies for different C/C composites could be calculated and were summarized in Table 2.

The fitting equations could be divided into three parts : the constant terms (A_0 and B_0) the activation energy terms (A_1 and B_1) and the temperature term (B_2). The constant terms depend on the intrinsic properties of specimens. The tested specimens were all carbon materials in this study, so the constant terms were supposed to be the same. The coefficient A_0 might be composed of the constant and the temperature terms, the values for the CC1000, CVI1000 and CC2600 were 19.44, 14.89 and 12.92, respectively. On the contrast, the coefficients B_0 were -0.216, -0.242, and -0.261. The variation of coefficient A_0 was larger than that of the coefficient B_0 .

The activation energy terms were determined by the activation energy of surface reaction. The activation energy was a constant value for a specific reaction. The activation energy of carbon-oxygen reaction was about 40~80 kcal/mole. The non-crystalline carbon structure and the different carbon bonding would affect the value of the activation energy.

The temperature term was changed with temperature. The B_2 values were 2.61, 1.95, and 1.74 for CC1000, CVI1000, and CC2600, respectively. The oxidation rates of CC1000 were proportional to $T^{2.61}$, and the temperature showed more predominate influence on the oxidation rates for CC1000. The surface area, gaseous concentrations on the specimen surface and in the

bulk stream, and the diffusion rates were all determined by the temperature; meanwhile, these factors showed high effect on the oxidation rates.

CONCLUSIONS

The oxidation behaviors of carbon materials in isothermal and non-isothermal oxidation tests could be divided into two stages : the surface oxygen-carbon reaction controlled stage and the gaseous diffusion controlled stage. The 1000°C carbonized C/C composites were not oxidized until 500°C; however, the CVI C/C composites densified at 1000°C or graphitized at 2600°C would not be oxidized until 700°C. The rate constant and activated energy could be correlated to the intrinsic properties of C/C composites.

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Table 1. Coefficients of two fitting equations and fitting ranges

Materials	A_0	A_1	B_0	B_1	B_2	fitting range
CC1000	19.44	-25216	-0.2161	-22883	2.61	570-700 °C
CVI1000	14.89	-22589	-0.2415	-21288	1.95	720-850 °C
CC2600	12.92	-21233	-0.2611	-20214	1.74	700-920 °C

Table 2. Activation energy of various C/C composites (unit : kcal/mole).

Material	equation A	equation B
CC1000	50.10	45.47
CVI1000	44.88	42.30
CC2600	42.19	40.17

Figure 1. The diagram of thermogravimetric measurement

Figure 2. The weight loss of carbon/carbon composites under the isothermal oxidations at 600, 650, 700, 800, 900 and 1000.

Figure 3. The comparison of analysis for isothermal and non-isothermal oxidation tests for CC 1000.

Figure 4. The comparison of weight loss profile during non-isothermal oxidation tests for various carbon/carbon composites.